

STUDY OF RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND SELF CONCEPT OF B.Ed TEACHER TRAINEE

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Abstract

The present study was designed for finding the relationship between total Emotional Intelligence and total Self Concept of B.Ed. teacher trainees. A sample of 60 B. Ed. teacher trainees from College of Education, Nasik was taken for the collection of data. The statistical techniques Coefficient of correlation and t-value were used for analyzing the data. The findings were exists a significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Self Concept of B.Ed. teacher trainees.

Introduction

Nowadays Emotional Intelligence and Self Concept is considered vital for success in any field even also in the teaching training. Both affect the teaching attitude of B.Ed. teacher trainees. When Emotional Intelligence and Self Concept work together, we are able to increase the potential among the B.Ed. teacher trainees. The main highlight of this study is to see the relationship between emotional Intelligence and Self Concept of B.Ed. teacher trainees.

Statement of the problem

To Study the Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and self Concept of B.Ed. Teacher Trainees

Operational Definitions of Specific Terms:

Emotional Intelligence:

Emotional Intelligence means the ability to understand and express oneself, to relate to others, to adopt to change and to solve problems of personal and social nature and also to deal with strong emotions and control ones impulses.

Self Concept :

Self concept is the individual's way of looking at himself/herself. It also signifies his/her way of thinking, feeling and behaving.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To study the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Self Concept of Female B. Ed. Teacher trainees.
- 2) To study the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Self concept of male B.Ed. teacher trainees.
- 3) To study the relationship between Emotional intelligence and Self Concept of total B. Ed. teacher trainees.

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Hypotheses:

- 1) There is no significant relationship between the Emotional Intelligence and Self Concept of Female B. Ed. teacher trainees.
- 2) There is no significant relationship between the Emotional Intelligence and Self Concept of Male B. Ed. teacher trainees.
- 3) There is no significant relationship between the Emotional Intelligence and Self Concept of total B. Ed. teacher trainees.

Research Methodology:

By considering the objectives of the study and the resources available to collect the relevant data, the Survey Method was used.

Sample:

The sample of the study consists of 60 B.Ed. teacher trainees. Out of which 30 male and 30 female teacher trainees studying in the College of Education, Nashik.

Tools used for Study:

- 1) Emotional Intelligence Scale of Anukool Hyde, Sanjyot Pethe and Upinder Dhar.
- 2) Dr. Rajkumar Saraswats Self Concept Questionnaire.

Procedure of the Study

Initially Anukool Hyde, Sanjyot Pethe and Upinder Dhar's Emotional Intelligence Scale was administered on 30 male and 30 female B. Ed. teacher trainees. Afterwards Dr. Rajkumar Saraswat's Self Concept Questionnaire was administered on 30 male and 30 female teacher trainees. The responses of Emotional Intelligence Scale and Self concept Questionnaire were scored, tabulated and analyzed by using Statistical techniques.

Testing of hypothesis

Hypothesis-1: There is no significant relationship between the Emotional Intelligence and

Self Concept of Female B. Ed. teacher trainees.

Sr.No.	Variable	N	Mean	r	t _r -Value
1	Emotional Intelligence	30	124.05	0.43	2.52
2	Self Concept	30	213.37		

At 28 degrees of freedom table t-value at 0.05 level of significance is 2.048 and the calculated t-value is 2.52. The calculated t-value is greater than the table t-value. Therefore the hypothesis-1 is rejected. Therefore it was inferred that there was a significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Self Concept of B.Ed. female teacher trainees.

Hypothesis-2: There is no significant relationship between the Emotional Intelligence and

Self Concept of Male B. Ed. teacher trainees.

Sr.No.	Variable	N	Mean	r	tr-Value
1	Emotional Intelligence	30	127.42	0.48	2.89
2	Self Concept	30	216.33		

At 28 degrees of freedom table t-value at 0.05 level of significance is 2.048 and the calculated t-value is 2.89. The hypothesis-2 is rejected because calculated t-value 2.89 is exceeding the table t-value 2.048. It was inferred that there was a significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Self Concept of B.Ed. Female teacher trainees.

Hypothesis-3: There is no significant relationship between the Emotional Intelligence and

Self Concept of total B. Ed. teacher trainees.

Sr.No.	Group	N	r	tr-Value
1	Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Self Concept of total B.Ed. teacher trainees	60	0.59	5.56

At 58 degrees of freedom table t-value at 0.05 level of significance is 2.021 and the calculated t-value is 5.59. The calculated t-value is more than the table t-value. Therefore

the hypothesis-3 is rejected. Hence it was inferred that there was a significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Self Concept of total B.Ed. teacher trainees.

Findings of the Study:

1. There is a significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Self Concept of Female B.Ed. teacher trainees.
2. There is a significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Self Concept of Male B.Ed. teacher trainees.
3. There is a significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Self Concept of Total B.Ed. teacher trainees.

Implications of the Findings:

The findings of the study are likely to be importance to newly admitted teacher trainees for B.Ed.course, teacher educators, teacher training institutes and also to the different agencies which are concerned with education.

The study proved that there was a significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Self Concept of B.Ed. teacher trainees. Therefore it is very important for teacher trainees to correlate Emotional Intelligence and Self Concept to become a successful and effective teacher.

References

- 1 Best, J.W. and Kahn, J.V. (2010). **Research in Education** (10th ed.). New Delhi: PHI Learning Private Limited.
2. Garrette, H.E. (2006). **Statistics in Psychology and Education**. Delhi: Surjeet Publications.
3. Hyde,A. Pethe,S. and Dhar, U. (2005). **Manual for Emotional Intelligence Scale**. Agra: National Psychological Corporation.
3. Saraswat,R.K. (2005). **Manual for Self-Concept Questionnaire**. Agra: National

Psychological Corporation.

